

Inclined Intervention of Language, Literature and Ideologies

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Abstract: Language can't stand in isolation as it reflects too many aspects of life, such a transformation never stopped by time and tide. These spheres of activities tapped in texts as prose or poem in the form of language and literature. This literature witnessed too many voices ranging from rage to riches, capturing emotions that were born by the ideas of texts that have come into existence as literary works by the poets of each literary era, in turn this voice has transformed over a period as ideologies. Literary works: Macbeth, Lady Macbeth says "pour my spirits in thine ear" in Act 1, Scene 5 i.e. highlights her intense ambition. Robert Browning's *My Last Duchess* "I gave commands; Then all smiles stopped together" reveals the duke's cruel, possessive nature. O.Henry's *Animal Farm* "All animals are equal, but some animals are more equal than others" reflects corruption. A wide range of emotions and ideologies coexists in literary works. The aim of the study is to understand the inclined interventions of literature and ideologies in selected works.

Keywords: Language, literature, ideologies and emotions

Introduction:

Language and literature make hand in glove, as each of the lifestyle and walks of life it matters to passing the mode and lifelong experiences to generations to go. Language acts as mode and literature witness sequence of events that reflects emotional emergence. One such act always rooms to capture too many events. Capturing such events time to time reflects lifestyle that they own. Literature in the process captures An ideology that is a set of beliefs or values attributed to individual or group of people around, these attributes of beliefs and experienced knowledge. Ideologies are applied to all economic, political, or religious theories and policies. The term "ideology" and the system of ideas associated with it were developed in 1796 by Antoine Destutt de Tracy (1754–1836), French Enlightenment aristocrat and philosopher who crystallized his ideas while in prison. He devised the term for a "science of ideas", basing on the sensations that people experience as they interact with the material world and the ideas that form in their minds due to those sensations. His conceived of ideology as a liberal philosophy that would defend individual liberty, property, free markets, and constitutional limits on state power.

George Walford and Harold Walsby, who attempt to explore the relationships between ideology and social systems. David W. Minar describes six different ways the word ideology has been used: As a collection of certain ideas with certain kinds of content, usually normative; as the form or internal logical structure that ideas have within a set; by the role ideas play in human-social interaction, by the role ideas play in the structure of an organization, as meaning, whose purpose is persuasion; and as the locus of social interaction. An ideology is composed of four basic characteristics: it must have power over cognition; it must be capable of guiding one's evaluations, it must provide guidance towards action; and it must be logically coherent. Looking at the idea of ideology and its significance, it matters to study how language, literature and ideologies are interconnected and inclined factors. How a text can be viewed with in the coherence of literary works like O.Henry's *Animal Farm* "All animals are equal, but some animals

are more equal than others”, My Last Duchess “I gave commands; Then all smiles stopped together” and many more.

Discussion:

Feminism is both an ideology and a social/political movement aimed at establishing equal social, political, and economic rights for all genders. It acts as an ideology by analyzing, questioning, and challenging patriarchal structures and gender-based discrimination. From the first wave feminists to the third wave of feminists’ movement wants basic access of education to individual empowerment. Looking at each of the aspirations, women always wanted to liberate themselves from the stereotype of approach of women. The persuasion and social interaction support study of ideologies as stated In Systematic ideology is a study of ideologies founded in the late 1930s in and around London, England by Harold Walsby, George Walford and others. It seeks to understand the origin and development of ideologies.

Lady Macbeth wife of Macbeth is ambitious and wanted her husband to become the king. On the other hand, Macbeth was loyal to king, Duncan. After the battle Duncan had rewarded Macbeth's bravery by making him Thane of Cawdor .as similar to the weird sisters, three witches who prophesy “They met me in the day of success, and I have learned by the perfectest report they have more in them than mortal knowledge. When I burned in desire to question them further, they made themselves air...”. Lady Macbeth receives a letter from Macbeth about the prophecy of three witches and Duncan's imminent arrival in the castle. She finds it is not Macbeth desired position just to be Thane of Cawdor but to become king. She explores her ambitious wish for Macbeth to be a king and not Malcolm the eldest son of Duncan. Furthermore, she manipulates and provokes the fantasized Macbeth’s earliest intentions of murdering Duncan and becoming king. Likewise, she finds her husband a cold blood and lack of ambitions. Her constant questioning of his courage and being manhood win him over. “Yet do I fear thy nature; It is too full o’ th’ milk of human kindness to catch the nearest way: thou wouldst be great, Art not without ambition, but without the illness should attend it. What thou wouldst highly, that wouldst thou holily; wouldst not play false, and yet wouldst wrongly win. Thou’ld’st have, great Glamis, that which cries, “Thus thou must do,” if thou have it, and that which rather thou dost fear to do, than wishest should be undone. Hie thee hither, That I may pour my spirits in thine ear ...” finally in the night, they murder Duncan.

She urges the three witches to unsex her to kill the Duncan. Finally, the urge for male characteristic features was on high in Lady Macbeth. Clear identification that there exists some gender-based inequalities, either in terms of physical strength or a heroic act significantly associated with the other gender brings a thought-provoking gender-based feminist’s movements.

“My Last Duchess” a dramatic monologue also reflects how Victorian social norms deprived women to be fully independent human being. Duke of Ferrara’s objectification and dehumanization of the woman's character Duchess. By controlling Duchess freedom behind the curtain, Victorian society believed that women are objects to be controlled, possessed, and discarded. “... This grew; I gave commands. Then all smiles stopped together. There she stands...”

Duke wanted Duchess as an object and even the new wife he aspires to marry should also fulfill his set of criteria i.e. “... Of mine for dowry will be disallowed; Though his fair daughter’s self, as I avowed At starting, is my object.”

The objectification of women in *My Last Duchess* is sensed as urge for change in lifestyle i.e. of ideology, by the role ideas play in human-social interaction, and by the role ideas play in the structure of an organization in David W. Minar's describing in six different ways the word ideology has been used: Ideology as the locus of social interaction and the structure of an organization in George Orwell's "Animal Farm" a blend of understanding to Literature and ideologies. *Animal Farm* is an allegorical novella, Napoleon a pig who turns out to be totalitarian dictatorship. The shift in commands over a period reflects failure or supremacy of one ideological school over the other. The core principles of Animalism, the seven commandments establishes to ensure equality and prevent human-like corruption: Whatever goes upon two legs is an enemy, Whatever goes upon four legs or has wings is a friend, No animal shall wear clothes, No animal shall sleep in a bed, No animal shall drink alcohol, No animal shall kill any other animal, and All animals are equal. Later with fourth commandment about beds becomes "No animal shall sleep in a bed with sheets"., fifth commandment about alcohol consumption becomes "No animal shall drink alcohol to excess", sixth commandment about killing "No animal shall kill any other animal without cause" and seventh commandment about equality becomes "All animals are equal, but some animals are more equal than others". Old major's dream remains unfulfilled i.e. No human beings to oppress or control them. Old Major, conducts a meeting in a big barn and addresses his lifelong dream, animals live together with no human beings to oppress or control them. He teaches the animals a song called "Beasts of England,". All animals get convinced with Major's vision. Three pigs Napoleon, Snowball, and Squealer frames main principles into a philosophy called Animalism. The animals defeat the farmer Mr. Jones in a battle, running him off the land. They rename the property Animal Farm and dedicate themselves to achieving and follow Major's dream. Snowball contributes to teach all the animals to read, and Napoleon takes a group of young puppies to educate them in the principles of Animalism. When Mr. Jones retires to win his property the animals defeat him, names the victory as the Battle of the Cowshed.

Napoleon and Snowball involve in reforms in their own way Snowball plans to support electricity generation by constructing windmill, but Napoleon solidly opposes the plan. Napoleon does conspiracy and assumes leadership of Animal Farm and declares that there will be no more meetings in a democratic way. He gives all power to the pigs and alone pigs will make all the decision for the good of every animal. Napoleon takes all credits of good in his books and defects and threats into Snowball. Napoleon claims that Snowball returned to the farm to sabotage the windmill. A shift of animals believes "Napoleon is always right", Napoleon begins expanding his powers, rewriting history to make Snowball a villain and threat to the animal farm. Napoleon drifts away from commands i.e. whatever goes upon two legs is an enemy, whatever goes upon four legs or has wings is a friend, no animal shall wear clothes, no animal shall sleep in a bed, no animal shall drink alcohol. He adopts and starts act more like a human being sleeping in a bed, drinking whiskey, and engaging in trade with neighbouring farmers of same dictators. Napoleon has sold his most loyal and long-suffering worker to a glue maker to get money for whiskey. Years pass on Animal Farm, and the pigs become more like human beings walking upright, carrying whips, and wearing clothes. Eventually, the seven principles of Animalism, known as the Seven Commandments and inscribed on the side of the barn, become reduced to a single principle reading "all animals are equal, but some animals are more equal than others."

A Room of One's Own, women urge women to give a voice in the lines "One cannot think well, love well, sleep well, if one has not dined well." The transition of literary works closes witnessed feminist aspirations time to time. Nora Helmer, a character in A Doll's House, wife of Torvald Helmer is treated like doll, her identity as women is always sensed as doll with no self-identity. Her sacrifices as wife and homemaker are never appreciated. Nora as a caring wife she looks after her husband by illegally borrowing money. In the process, she suffers the pain of Krogstad blackmailing. At last Torvald acquaints self with the letter about Nora's illegal borrowing of money to serve the needs of the family in a dire position. He accuses Nora a hypocrite and a liar and complains that she has ruined his happiness. He threatens her that she will not be allowed to raise their children under her characteristic influence. Nora despite their eight years of marriage, walks out, slamming the door behind her for her husband's disputed comments on her characterization. Nora's father and her husband's approach to her have always been a doll. They both don't let her find her identity and potentiality.

Conclusion:

Ideologies frame individual behaviour, societal norms, and political decision-making which promote unity and social cohesion by offering a shared identity, over a period such ideologies are accepted and rejected. However, ideologies always rooms for new ideologies. Literature witnesses too many voices ranging from rage to riches, capturing emotions that were born by the ideas of texts that have come into existence as literary works by the poets of each literary era and ideological transforms and implementations.

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